

THE EURO-GLOBAL PLATFORM FOR MECHANISM-BASED DRUG REPURPOSING

REPO4EU News – April 2025

Dear colleague,

Welcome to the fifth edition of the REPO4EU Newsletter!

As we enter spring, the momentum around drug repurposing continues to build – and so does our community. In this issue, we're thrilled to spotlight some major developments: registration is now open for RExPO25 in Barcelona, our flagship event bringing together the full spectrum of stakeholders in systems medicine, AI, and drug repurposing. We've also kicked off critical discussions on sustainable models for repurposing with a powerful policy event in Brussels, launched the REPO4EU Podcast, and introduced DrugRepoChatter, a new AI tool designed to support researchers in navigating the ever-growing scientific literature. Finally, we're excited to announce the official launch of Network Medicine, our Diamond Open Access journal – and we're actively welcoming contributions from across the field.

Prof, Harald Schmidt
MD, PhD, PharmD
Coordinator of REPO4EU – Maastricht University

RexPO25

THE 4TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
SYSTEMS MEDICINE, AI & DRUG REPURPOSING

BARCELONA
SEPTEMBER 24-26 2025

Get ready for REXPO25 this September in Barcelona

Registrations are now open to join us at REXPO25 –the fourth edition of our annual conference on Systems Medicine, AI & Drug Repurposing–, an event that brings together world-leading experts from across the entire drug repurposing ecosystem, including clinicians, researchers, SMEs, policymakers and patient representatives.

This year's edition is taking place in Barcelona on 24-26 September, and you cannot miss it! Our call for abstracts is also live – we'll be covering a wide range of topics, from rare diseases, network medicine and precision diagnostics, all the way to patient engagement and sustainable reimbursement models. If this sounds interesting, make sure to check out our preliminary agenda and take advantage of our early-bird discounts to secure your spot now!

This is REXPO25

Kicking off the conversation around sustainable models for drug repurposing

How can we build a patient-centered approach to drug repurposing? How can we find the balance between providing fair return on investments for companies backing repurposed drugs while ensuring patients can afford these treatments? How can regulators and researchers collaborate to reshape the future of medicine?

These critical questions brought together top EU policymakers, regulators, patient advocates and industry leaders at the first hybrid policy event hosted by REPO4EU in Brussels on 15 January 2025. Click below for a recap of the event full of expert insights on key topics like stimulating commercial investment, harmonizing the regulatory landscape, integrating the patients' perspective and advocating for fair reimbursement policies.

[Read more](#)

[REPO4EU The Podcast has just launched – tune in to our first episode](#)

Welcome to the REPO4EU Podcast – the programme that brings you closer to the latest innovations, research and developments happening in drug repurposing across the globe through interviews with leading academic voices. For our inaugural episode, we had the pleasure of sitting down with Dr. Ana Casas, Assistant Professor in Neurology at University Hospital Essen in Germany, where she leads a research group focused on Network pharmacology for neurovascular diseases.

[Listen to the episode](#)

[Introducing DrugRepoChatter, an AI tool for drug repurposing researchers](#)

Sifting through the vast amount of scientific literature can be overwhelming, especially in fast-evolving fields like drug repurposing. To tackle this, experts from the REPO4EU Consortium have joined forces to develop [DrugRepoChatter](#), an AI-powered timesaver tool that helps researchers navigate through the relevant literature for mechanism-based drug repurposing in a faster and more efficient way.

Bioinformatician and GenAI expert Dr. Fernando M. Delgado-Chaves has led the development of DrugRepoChatter – follow the link for an in-depth interview in which he explains his approach to designing the tool, how it works and its capabilities.

[Check it out](#)

Our Network Medicine journal is looking for contributors

We are extremely pleased to announce the launch of [Network Medicine](#), a Diamond Open Access, peer-reviewed journal focused on interdisciplinary approaches to exploiting the power of big data by applying network science and systems thinking to medicine.

Network Medicine publishes high quality basic science, translational and clinical research: we are looking for research articles, review articles, mini-reviews, rapid communications, brief reports, technology reports, hypothesis articles, perspectives and letters to the editor. This is a great opportunity to submit your research – click below for the full details on our call for papers.

[Learn more](#)

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